

Dipole Moments of Hydrogen Bonded Complexes : Chloroform-Nitriles in Cyclohexane

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Formation of hydrogen bond is accompanied by the changes in polarisabilities of the donor and acceptor, resulting in the corresponding changes in the electrical properties of the components. The polarisability and the dipole moment of hydrogen bonded/charge transfer systems provide valuable information about the nature of binding in the ground state of the complexes. Many researchers had determined the dipole moments of hydrogen bonded/charge transfer complexes in the ground state. However most of the researchers had used carbon tetrachloride as solvent. But carbon tetrachloride, a weak electron acceptor, interacts with the reactants. So the dipole moment values reported in the literature are not the true dipole moments of the systems¹⁻⁴. Therefore, if one is interested in obtaining true dipole moment, a relatively less polar non-interacting solvent should be used. The present communication reports the dipole moment values of a few systems (binary and ternary) in cyclohexane, a relatively non-interacting medium. The systems chosen are chloroform-acetonitrile and chloroform-phenylacetonitrile in cyclohexane.

Results and Discussion

The dipole moment (μ) values of CHCl_3 , CH_3CN and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ in cyclohexane are found to be 1.10 (0.9-1.86)⁴, 4.27 (4.32)³ and 3.80 D respectively. For binary solutions the linear plot of weight fractions (W_2) of solutes against $(\epsilon_{12}-\epsilon_1)$ or $(n_{12}^2 - n_1^2)$ suggests that there is no specific interactions between polar solutes and the solvent. However, the solvent seems to be involved in the polarisation as the reported dipole moment of all the

three liquids are higher in carbon tetrachloride than in cyclohexane (observed) which go in parallel with the theory of Higasi⁵. The dipole moment of phenylacetonitrile is lower than that of acetonitrile. The π -inductive effect of the benzene nuclei and mesomeric (+M) interaction lead to reduction in the bond moment in phenyl substituted nitriles.

The dipole moment (μ) of $\text{CHCl}_3-\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ in cyclohexane is 5.57 (± 0.01)D. Jumper and Howard¹ reported 5.12D for this system in CCl_4 whereas the reported theoretical value for $\text{CHCl}_3-\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ system is 5.45 D. The experimentally determined μ for the adduct is 0.20D higher than the 'additive' value of the components and this indicates that the adduct is more polarised⁶. The calculated value using modified Onsager equation⁸ is 5.61D. The deviation by 0.04D is attributed to the experimental limitations involved. The dipole moment of the ternary system, $\text{CHCl}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$ in cyclohexane is found to be 5.06 (± 0.01)D which is 0.16D higher than the 'additive' value. The modified Onsager equation assigns the value to be 5.09D. The π -electron density on the benzene nuclei reduces the extent of interaction between chloroform and nitriles through substitution by a phenyl group does not lead to any unexpected change in the formation of an 'adduct'. This is established firmly when ir frequencies for both the complexed and uncomplexed systems are correlated. In ternary system, the C-H stretching frequency in CHCl_3 decreases by ca. 10 cm^{-1} while that of CN stretching frequency of nitriles increases by ca. 20 cm^{-1} (in both the cases). The increase in the CN frequency of nitriles indicates a strengthening of the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bond. The decrease in ν_{CH} for CHCl_3 is due to decrease in the electron density. The molecular electrostatic potential around the

nitriles indicates N lone-pair as the preferential site for hydrogen bond formation⁵ and thus it is reasonable to expect the 'adduct' formation between chloroform and nitriles with H atom of CHCl₃ molecule near the N atom of the nitrile via hydrogen bonding of the type : R-H₂C≡N...HC-Cl₃. The approach of donor towards an acceptor results in mutual distortion of the charge distribution in both the components which contributes to the true dipole moment of the system.

Experimental

Cyclohexane (SISCO, spectro-grade), acetonitrile (S. D., spectro-grade), phenylacetonitrile (I.D.P.L., A.R.) and chloroform (Sarabhai, spectro-grade) were purified using the standard procedures⁹; their refractive indices and densities agree well with the literature values : cyclohexane $n_d = 1.424$ (1.424), $\rho = 0.7768$ (0.7788)¹⁰; acetonitrile $n_d = 1.343$ (1.444), $\rho = 0.7768$ (0.7785)¹⁰; chloroform $n_d = 1.444$ (1.444) $\rho = 1.4727$ (1.4742)¹⁰ and phenyl acetonitrile $n_d = 1.523$ (1.523), $\rho = 1.018$ (1.015)¹¹ at 298.15 K.

Solutions were prepared by weight. The dielectric constants of the solutions were measured using a DM01 (WTW GmbH, Germany) instrument fitted with cylindrical gold plated condenser cell (type MFL-1). The instrument was operated on a superposition (beat) method with a measuring sensitivity of $\Delta\epsilon/\epsilon = 10^{-5}$. The temperature of the solution in the cell was maintained at 298.15 K. Density and refractive index of the solutions at 298.15 K were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel 3 ml pycnometer and an Abbe 82205 refractometer respectively. Infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer fitted with AgCl cell.

The dipole moment (μ) of a binary system was determined using the equation¹²,

$$\mu = [27 kT/4\pi N_0 \cdot 1/d_1 (\epsilon_1 + 2) (a_e - a_n) M_2]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where k , T and N_0 are Boltzmann constant, temperature (K) and Avagadro number respectively and ϵ_1 is the dielectric constant of the solvent at temperature T , d_1 the density of the solvent, M_2 the molecular weight of the liquid (solute), a_e the slope of the curve $(\epsilon_{12} - \epsilon_1)$ against weight fraction (W_2) of

the solute, a_n the slope of the curve $(n_{12}^2 - n_1^2)$ against weight-fraction (W_2) of the solute, ϵ_{12} the dielectric constant of the solutions and n_{12} the refractive index of the solutions.

The dipole moment (μ) of the ternary system was determined using the modified equation of Onsager and Kirkwood¹²,

$$\mu = 3/2 [(P_{2\alpha} - P_a - P_e) kT / \pi N_0] \quad (2)$$

For a ternary system, A and D in a nonpolar solvent S, using mixture law of specific polarisation and law of mass action, the polarisation of the solution (P_{soln}) is given by

$$P_{\text{soln}} = X_S P_S + (X_D - X_{AD}) P_D + (X_A - X_{AD}) P_A + X_{AD} P_{AD} \quad (3)$$

$$P_{AD} = 1/X_{AD} [P_{\text{soln}} - X_S P_S - (X_D - X_{AD}) P_D - (X_A - X_{AD}) P_A] \quad (4)$$

If the concentration of the donor D is in excess, then the above equation reduces to

$$P_{AD} = 1/X_{AD} [P_{\text{soln}} - X_S P_S - X_D P_D - X_A P_A] \quad (5)$$

where P_{AD} is the polarisation due AD ; P_S , P_A and P_D are polarisations due to solvent, acceptor and donor respectively and X_S , X_A and X_D are their mole fractions. P_{soln} is then obtained from equation,

$$P_{\text{soln}} = (\epsilon_{\text{soln}} - 1) / (\epsilon_{\text{soln}} + 2) \cdot \sum_1 (X_i M_i) / d_{\text{soln}} \quad (6)$$

With one assumption that one of the components, viz., A has been completely complexed for $X_D \gg X_A$ (in excess of solvent), the polarisation due to AD, i.e. P_{AD} instead of $P_{2\alpha}$ and P_d , the distortion polarisation ($P_a + P_e$), obtained from refractive index measurements, are used in equation (2) to calculate μ for the ternary system.

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